

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B415
 Date: 05 Nov 2008
 Take Off: 09:12:40
 Landing: 14:33:09
 Flight Time 5h 20m 29s

Campaign: VOCALS – POC Flight 2

Operating Area: S.E. Pacific Ocean off the coast of northern Chile

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Steve Abel	Met Office	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Grant Allen	Manchester University	
6	Flight Manager	Stephen Devereau	FAAM	
7	Core Chem / AVAPS	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
11	ARIES / MARSS	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
12	CAPS / 2DS	Hugh Coe	Manchester University	
13	AMS	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
14	Wet Neph / PSAP / Filters	James Bowles	Met Office	
15	VACC	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University	
16	Mission Scientist 3	Alan Gadian	Leeds University	
17	CVI	Paul Barrett	Met Office	
18	Mission Scientist 4	Patricia Krecl	Leeds University	
19	Mission Scientist 5	Thomas Toniazza	University of Reading	

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B415
 Date: 5th November 2008
 Project: VOCALS
 Location: Arica, Chile

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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065719		Start-Up	0.00 kft	026	18'21.00S, 70'20.21W
085851		Start-Up	0.11 kft	026	engine start
090700		!	0.11 kft	026	taxy
090757		ASP	0.11 kft	020	opened
091240		T/O	0.51 kft	202	
091240	093400	Profile 1	0.56 - 22.0 kft	210	
091530		!	3.1 kft	258	Nevzorov/JW zero
091803		!	5.8 kft	253	JW zero
092300		!	10.8 kft	257	Nevzorov/JW zero
093400	104034	Run 1	22.0 kft		
093959		Sonde 1	22.0 kft	257	
094625		!	22.1 kft	260	Nevzerov/JW zero
095500		Sonde 2	22.0 kft	254	
101640		Sonde 3	22.0 kft	258	
101736		Sonde 3	22.1 kft	260	101550
102500		Sonde 4	22.0 kft	254	
103241		!	22.0 kft	261	retract BBR
103400		!	22.1 kft	260	JW zero
103747		!	22.0 kft	257	Heimann cal
103959		Sonde 5	22.0 kft	259	
104640	105525	Profile 2	9.8 - 1.9 kft	272	
105533	110224	Run 2	1.9 kft	270	
105734		!	1.9 kft	265	JW zero
110349	111748	Run 3	1.9 kft	084	
111256		!	1.9 kft	075	Heimann cal
111756	113128	Run 3	1.8 - 0.87 kft	077	run eased down from 2
113250	113626	Profile 3	0.92 - 4.7 kft	260	
113759	114211	Run 4	4.8 - 4.9 kft	065	
113930		!	4.8 kft	075	JW zero
114336	121422	Run 5	3.3 kft	265	
121422	121745	Profile 4	3.4 - 6.3 kft	258	
122017	122757	Profile 5	6.3 - 0.05 kft	077	
122103		!	5.7 kft	081	JW zero
122758	123505	Profile 6	0.05 - 6.3 kft	086	50ft
122924		!	0.80 kft	082	JW zero
123425		!	5.8 kft	070	JW zero
123506	124318	Profile 7	6.3 - 0.05 kft	070	
124150		!	0.37 kft	073	JW zero
124318	124901	Profile 8	0.05 - 5.7 kft	071	
125051	125551	Run 6	3.4 kft	254	
125722	130210	Profile 9	3.1 - 0.05 kft	068	
130330	131332	Run 7	1.4 - 1.5 kft	085	

131332	132855	Profile 10	1.5 - 23.0 kft	091
132006		!	10.9 kft	080 JW zero
132913	140924	Run 8	23.1 - 23.0 kft	082
133200		Sonde 6	23.0 kft	090
133906		Sonde 7	23.0 kft	087
134708		Sonde 8	23.0 kft	087
135400		Sonde 9	23.0 kft	083
140100		Sonde 10	23.0 kft	083
140938	143309	Profile 11	22.9 - 0.00 kft	078 at landing
143309		Land	0.00 kft	019 Arica

B415 Track 05-NOV-08

SCAR -> SCDA - Overview

NavData Cycle 2008-11 Expires: Thursday, 20 November 2008.

Scale: 1:4593479 (1 inch = 63.00 naut mi). Printed on 04 Nov 2008

7 6 9 9 6 ; 6 8

FliteStar 9.4.2.0

Sortie Flight B415
5th November 2008.
VOCALS POC Mission 2

T/O **0600 local (0900 UTC)**
Land **1100 local (1400 UTC)**

Mission Scientists: Steven Abel, Grant Allen, Alan Gadian, Patricia Krecl, Thomas Toniazzo

Waypoints:

ZULU: 79°W 20°S

Note that ZULU should be at the boundary of a POC; if necessary this point can be repositioned within box defined by 76-82°W 19-21°S. Note that if point ZULU is 82°W 20°S then add approx 30 mins to transit time.

Aims:

To measure the dynamics, microphysical and large-scale structure, chemistry and processes of a cluster of closed convective cells (a.k.a. Pockets of Open Cells - POCS) embedded in marine stratocumulus off the West Coast of Chile.

Location:

South East Pacific off the West Coast of Chile (point Zulu).

Latest satellite Image (to be inserted):

Flight Summary:

1. Take off and profile ascent 1000 ft/min immediately to FL230 [23 min; T=23 min]
2. Transit towards point ZULU, dropping a total of 5 sondes. [49 min; T=72 min]
3. Profile descent at 1000 ft/min to reach point ZULU at 5000 ft (or above cloud). [18 min; T=90 min]
4. Fly a 20 minute leg above cloud crossing the boundary between the POC and surrounding overcast Sc drifting with the mean wind. [20 min; T=110 min]
4. Descend and turn 180 degrees to 1000 ft (or just below cloud) within the POC and fly a 30-minute run from clear air towards the overcast Sc (POC boundary at the mid-point of the run) drifting with the mean wind [30 min; T=140 min]
5. Ascend and turn 180 degrees to 3000 ft (or to an altitude within cloud) and fly a 30-minute run at cloud level starting in overcast Sc and heading into POC (POC boundary at the mid-point of the run) drifting with the mean wind [30 min; T=170 min]

6. Continue legs across boundary as defined by mission scientist (possibly saw tooth leg) as time permits [40 min; T=210 min].
7. Turn to Arica recovery radial and descend to minimum safe altitude and perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min to FL 100, followed by a climb to FL 230. [15 min; T=225 min].
8. High level recovery to Arica (FL 230) dropping a total of 5 sondes. [75 min; T=300 min].

Key Instrument Details:

SWS – as per instructions.

ARIES – as per instructions

CVI - During high level operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating.

CVI – during in cloud runs operate in counterflow mode

Wet Neph – operated during all of low level non-cloud runs

AMS – operate from Rosemount during aerosol and high level runs and profiles; operate on CVI during in cloud runs

Filters – Vent the inlet line in the absence of filter immediately after cloud run prior to starting filter run for between 2 and 5 minutes. 2x filters on sub-cloud leg. 1 either side of boundary.

Sortie Flight B415
5th November 2008.
VOCALS POC Mission 2

T/O **0600 local (0900 UTC)**
Land **1100 local (1400 UTC)**

Mission Scientists: Steven Abel, Grant Allen, Alan Gadian, Patricia Krecl, Thomas Toniazzo

Waypoints:
ZULU: 78°W 20°S

Aims:
To measure the dynamics, microphysical and large-scale structure, chemistry and processes of a cluster of closed convective cells (a.k.a. Pockets of Open Cells - POCS) embedded in marine stratocumulus off the West Coast of Chile.

Location:
South East Pacific off the West Coast of Chile (point Zulu).

GOES CH1 visible satellite imagery at 13:45 UTC with sampled POC feature circled in red:

Flight Summary:

1. Performed a profile ascent at 1000 ft/min from Arica to FL220. Large variation in the moisture profile on the ascent. Dry layer at 750 – 550 mbar. Aerosol layer at approx 700 mbar.
2. Released 4 dropsondes on the transit towards point ZULU (no wind data on sonde #2). 8/8 Sc near coast with patchy Ci above. Sc became broken in patches in area consistent with the coastal “bite” – approx 74°42’W, 19°18’S – and the wind direction changed from NW’ly to SE’ly as transited from West to East across the coastal “bite”. Cloud then became more uniform again to the West.
3. Small POC area identified visually – see satellite image above. Then performed a profile descent into the more overcast Sc on the SW side of POC. Cloud top 3800’, cloud base 3000’. Droplet conc ~ 200 cc-1, MVD ~ 15 um.
4. Performed a sub-cloud SLR at 2000’ away from POC region. CCN ~ 45 cc-1, CN ~ 400 cc-1 at start of run. The CCN conc increased to 240 cc-1 along the run away from the POC. Aerosol composition was mainly sulphate with small traces of organics.
5. SLR at 2000’. We flew through the SW’ern boundary of the POC, through the POC and into the overcast Sc on the NE edge of the POC. Cloud base in POC is lower than surrounding Sc. Some heavy drizzle (2DC reporting 40L-1 600 um drops) in the POC region and lower accumulation mode aerosol concentrations – CCN 2 cc-1, CN 650 cc-1 than below surrounding Sc.
6. In cloud run at 3500’. Droplet concentrations were typically ~ 150 cc-1 and MVD ~ 15 um in the surrounding Sc region compared to 40 cc-1 and 30 um in the POC region. Intermittent drizzle in the Sc and heavier spells of drizzle in the POC. Cloud layer within POC is only a few hundred feet thick.
7. Performed a saw tooth leg through the POC region from 6500’ to 50’. Clear reduction in the sub-cloud CCN conc and a corresponding increase in the CN conc within the POC compared to the surrounding Sc. Drizzle in POC evaporating and leading to a decoupling of the BL. This resulted in small patches of cloud at about 1000’ with main cloud base ~ 2700’. Profile showed a more well mixed BL in the surrounding Sc regions.
8. A five minute SLR within the cloud layer in the POC was then performed (Droplet Conc ~ 70 cc-1, MVD ~ 30 um) followed by a profile descent to 50’ and a 10 minute SLR in the sub-cloud layer at 1500’ across the NE POC boundary and returning towards Arica under the surrounding Sc. CCN and sulphate concs increased along this run, with CN and drizzle decreasing.
9. Final profile ascent to FL230 and transit to Arica. 5 more dropsondes were released and a profile descent to Arica airport made.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.415...

Date ..5/11/08.....

Name ..STEVE ABEL.....

Page of 8

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Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
091319	T70				Lot of structure in profile
	P11	Ascent to F220			Humidity variation all way up from above BL to 750mbar and then dry layer with big T inversion. Moist again at 550mbar
092000					Aerosol layer neph shows sea similar at all λ → large particles. ~2500 - 3000m.
093634					Sun coming up - looks like extensive Sc below us. Bit of Ci above us.
093959			257		Sonde 1 18.85 72.4W
095500			254		Sonde 2 19.15 73.7W ↳ No winds on sonde 2
100133					Some small openings in Sc → consistent with coast where cloud changes at edge of coastal bite that we've seen in satellite imagery the last few days.
100505					Grant looking at latest sat pic Modify point Zulu to 78W 20S to predicted boundary of POC.
100657					2 nd Pic taken of broken cloud in coastal bite region.
101205					2 nd pic taken of coastal bite → broken Sc.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...415.....

Date 5/11/08.....

Name STEVE ABEL.....

Page 2... of 8

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Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8. StratoCu 3/8. hazy. wind 240°/24kts
					Thomas noted changes in wind as crossed coastal bike region.
101736		FL270	260	19.55 75.6W	Sonde 3 in coastal bike region Slight delay for due to problems with sonde communications.
102500				19.75 76.4W	Sonde 4
103327					Cloud below looks more uniform again as we've gone away from "bike" region.
106640	P2↓	FL000			Descent to below cloud. Just passed over an opening in cloud → "PCC" type region.
		6000'			Passing into SC region Barndy 78.1W 20S Cloud top 3900' Cloud base 3000' LWC 0.4 gm ⁻³ MWD 15µm N 250cc ⁻¹ , COP 100cc ⁻¹ ↖ CCN 45cc ⁻¹ CN 380-420cc ⁻¹
105525	R2				R2 PCASP, CCN etc showing increase along run. [NO ₂ spike below cloud to 6ppb.]
105933					CCN 240 CN 860 cc ⁻¹ Mostly sulphate with a bit of organics

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.415... Date 5/11/08... Name STEVE ABEL Page 3... of 8

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					End of leg F1W 20S.
110349	R3	2000'			At end start of run small areas of sunlight reaching surface, and then becomes more overcast. CCN picked up a spike again at start of this run. Otherwise 45cc ⁻ over 400cc ⁻
111300					VACC seeing another rise into an aerosol. CCN showing very heterogeneous CCN 20cc ⁻ over 500cc ⁻ . 20S seeing some drizzle. Cloud base around more open region. is lower than surrounding sea.
111539					Significant drizzle on boundary 78.12'W 19.48'S = boundary
111737					Descend to 1500' to maintain below cloud. Boundary is aerosol more spread out than previous POC.
111928					CCN 2cc ⁻ CN 650cc ⁻ PCASP ↓ 20S seeing drizzle.
112118					Descend to 1000' to remain below cloud. Heavier drizzle reaching surface.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...415... Date ..5/11/08... Name ...STEVE ABEL... Page 4... of 8

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Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8. StratoCu 3/8. hazy. wind 240°/24kts
					Cloud base down to 1000'
					in places.
112520					40L ⁻ 600µm drizzle drop.
112934					CCN 20cc ⁻ CN dropped off
					Passed into hazy more
					overcast SE region.
					CCN 35cc ⁻ CN 300cc ⁻
					at end of run
113250	P31				Profile up through cloud
					Cloud base 3000'
					Cloud top 3900'
113759	R4	4900'			Run for Cui to set flows
					above cloud top
114336	RS	3500'			^{START OF RUN} CAS 220cc ⁻ MVD 15µm
					COP 80 cc ⁻ MVD 15µm
					FSSP 120 cc ⁻ MVD 15µm
					small drizzle drops ~ 150µm
					NO ₂ small peak ~ 2. Sp. 17'
					clouds
114926					COP concs dropped to 40cc ⁻ } Inlec?
					MVD increased to 30µm } Inlec?
					FTSP ~ 50cc ⁻
115049					Just near cloud tops and
					pop into small gap. Cloud
					thickness ~ 500'

1 1/4 Run 114336

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.4.15 Date ...5/11/08... Name ...STEVE ABEL... Page ...5... of 8

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
115313					4000' CDP MVD 30µm 5000' FSSP = Droplet curves dropped off and MVD increased in ROC region.
115536					WACC some sulphate but not huge amounts. Drizzle on windscreen
115533					Popping in and out of cloud. In gaps can see patches of cloud extending down to lower levels as in sub-cloud leg. where it was ~1000'
115904					ZDS and cloud physics. Significant drizzle in these thin clouds and low drop N.
120103					MVD falling back down again and N steadily rising. Drizzle more intermittent.
120800					Grant → sat pics show ROC fairly clear at 19-85 BW ⇒ modify direction of next leg to try and cross rain oper area

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...415... Date ...5/11/08... Name ..STEVE ABEL... Page ..6... of 8

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
121257					Drizzle fairly constant along run since last update. N and MVD variable in last 2 mins.
121622	P4↑	profile to 6500'			Cloud top ~ 4000'
122017	P5↓	6500 → 50'			Cloud top 6000' base 3100'
122255					Pic taken at overcast & end heading towards POC. CCN 70cc ⁻ CN 300cc ⁻ VACC CN same. NOx spiked 3ppb. AMS ^{picobarns} sulphate ~ 1/μg ⁻³ Wind speed at surface ~ 7ms ⁻¹ Profile shows no strong T inversion
122924	P6↑	50' → 6500'			Cloud base 300' Cloud top 4000'
1234		5700'			Pictures of POC - see gap and some Cu tops rising above main & deck
	P7↓				Cloud Cloud base 2800' CCN 10cc ⁻ CN 600cc ⁻ In POC region below cloud Pic taken can see cloud base lowering.
124108					CCN → 0cc ⁻ !! Drizzle ahead CN 50cc ⁻
		50'			Drizzle to right of us

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.4.15 Date 5/11/08 Name STEVEN ABEL Page 7 of 8

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
124401					Much more structure in T profile below 1000mbar. CCN increased at surface → possibly sea salt
124520	R57				See some small cloud (flood) cloud around → Main cloud base ~ 2700' but small stuff below ~ 1000' base. → Drizzle evaporation causing this → Decoupled layer.
125051	R6				5 min to leg in cloud. CN 600cc ⁻¹ , N ~ 70cc ⁻¹ CAS MVD ~ 30µm. Some drizzle - not huge amounts.
125722 125501	part part	Descend to 50'			Cloud base ~ 2500' Again see evidence of decoupled Q with scudgy cloud layer below main k. Drizzle on underside of 500' of aircraft see Looking to right the can see drizzle evaporating - 500'
130230 130600	R7	1500'			Sub cloud leg 10/600 cc ⁻¹ at start ^{increasing to} 30/320 cc ⁻¹ Going away from POC boundary and expect CCN ↑ CN ↓ Less evidence of decoupled layer or sig drizzle.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 415... Date 5/11/08..... Name STEVE ABEL..... Page 8 of 8

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
130712					CCN up to 40 cc ⁻¹ CN 250 cc ⁻¹ No drizzle. AMS ~ 0.5 μg m ⁻³ sulphate.
13053					CCN 55 cc ⁻¹ err ECN gradually increasing as ground E and CN ↓
131138					AMS and VACC seeing sulphate - high CCN CN 65/200 cc ⁻¹ c.f. 0.0 μg m ⁻³ in POC
131257					CCN CN 80/220 cc ⁻¹ AMS organics close to 100 μg m ⁻³ and sulphate concs increased along run.
131532	Prot	1500' →	FL230		Cloud base 3000' Cloud top 4100'
			FL230		Transit back to Arica dropping sondes
133200					Sonde 6 - 19.15 75.6W Sonde 7 - 19.15 74.9W
134708					Sonde 8 - 19.05 74.1W Sonde 9 - 18.95 73.5W
140100					Sonde 10 - 18.95 72.8W
140924	Pil ↓	FL230			Profiling into Arica.

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Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 415 Date 5/11/08 Name G. ALLEN Page 1 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
08:50	0	0		Arisea	Surface conditions: 1009 mb, 16.5°C, No w/c. Dew point: 9.6°C. Clear sky. Night take off. Down in 15 min.
9:12:51	P1↑	22000ft			T/o delayed due to cabing. 1st immersion at: 911mb, 2800ft at 12°C.
					Strong mid-level immersion at 7000ft associated with moist layer.
9:34	R1	22000ft			Lots of thermal / moisture structure
9:39					Sonde 1 away
10:07					Sonde 2 away
					Coastal cloud boundary at 74°42'W, 19°18'S. Observed as a partial clearing in SC below on the edge of the airmass.
					POC area reached at 10:35. Evidence by broken cloud and raised cu on deck.
	P2↓				
10:54	R2	2000ft	270°	203782V	15µm 0.25 → 0.45 LWC. CB = 3000ft, 3800ft. CCN = 44-50 counts. Total CN = 310-420. N = 10m ⁻¹ E 5m ⁻¹ CCN 240 / CN = 850 imbedded

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 415 Date 5/11/08 Name G. ALLEN Page 2 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
11:02		2000ft	W		End of R2
11:03	R3	2000ft	E	20°S, 79°W	Drizzle around, not as much as before. NO ₂ , aerosol spike just below cloud base! Again! NA > Spike. Although CCN has all repart increase, all Sulphate, with some organics.
11:10					CCN seeing same structure. 40/350.
11:16			Change to		Mid-point - Boundary at 78°12'W
11:18	R3		75°		19°48'S - Scan down to 1500ft. Continuation of run. 500. 2/150 - CCN? 0.1. ↓ 1000ft to stay below cloud.
11:24					NAIES fell over. Cloud physics spots to scale at 40/1000, 600 µm diam.
11:31:28	R3 end			19°56'S, 77°18'W	19°36'S, 77°18'W, end of run 3.
11:33	R3↑	6000ft	257°	" "	CB = 3000ft - CTH = 3900ft. No NO ₂ spike on way up, but core don't see on previous flight.
11:15					Investig on climb at 8700ft 3 min run S&L for CVI. 10°C increase.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 415 Date 5/11/08 Name G. ALLEN Page 3 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
11:43	R5	3300ft	257		CS 2/8 22x2 LWC 15µm
					In cloud
					Inversion at 1100m
					NO _x peak at 750M, just below inversion
					Throughout run. cloud is thinning but not completely clearing.
					Drizzle dia and H ₂ O decreasing
					200 at NE end → 100 m. 15µm
12:01					NE run: cloud physics agrees
12:14	P4↑	6500ft			4100ft CB. NO _x spike seen at 79.2°W and 19.8°S and another at Eastern edge at 77.5°W, 19.5°S (2ppbv). Repeated elevated NO _x at same location.
12:20	P5b.				To be cloud level
					3100ft 4200ft cloud base
					CCN, 70/100. NO _x 3ppbv.
					SO ₄ ~ 1µg/m ³
12:27	P5	50ft	85°		South pole pattern. NO _x spike seen again - Drizzle around lat
			70°		
12:30	P6↑	6500ft	70°	19°47' 78.48	On POC boundary 3100ft CB, CTH - 4000ft.
12:37	P7L	50ft	73°	19°36'W, 78.3°W	Crossing into POC boundary below cloud.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 415 Date 5/11/08 Name G. ALLEN Page 4 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
12:40					Nox below cloud again -
	R8				CCN reporting 0 CN,
12:46	6000ft			11°18'W, 77°48'W	CCN = 500 - Lowered CB and Heavy drizzle.
					3900ft
12:49	R8 ↓	3500ft		11°18'W, 77°48'W	In - cloud at 3500ft for 5 min run -
12:50	R6	3500ft	253°		35 µm dia, some drizzle ~ 90.
12:56	R9 ↓	50ft	84°		Turn for 5 min sawtooth CB - 2500ft.
13:03	R7	1500ft	85°		10 min run - below cloud - Lots of drizzle & decoupling - seen vertically and in top layer -
13:14	P10 ↑				Ascent to FL230 - CTH = 3000ft -
13:29	R8	2300ft	88°	11°6'53"W	S&L for droplet
13:32					Sonde away ✓
13:39					Sonde away ✓
13:47					Sonde away ✓
13:54					Sonde away ✓
14:05	1		84		During P10 ↑ we saw elevated CO at 1800m and 4-5km. 60ppbv, from 45ppbv. Only small. No aerosol trace.
14:01					Sonde away -
14:30					end of science aft propul into Nica -

VOCALS BAe-146 Instrument status Report

Date of report(UTC): 2008/11/05 17:30

Author of report: Steve Abel

Submitted at(UTC): 2008/11/05 17:35

Remaining flight hours: 25

General Comments:

After mission on Ilo pollution flight on 5/11/2008

INSTRUMENTS / SYSTEMS STATUS

 = no report

Meteorology / Navigation

1.	GPS (Patch)	Comment:	
2.	GPS (Cruciform)	Comment:	
3.	Temperature/Pressure	Comment:	
4.	Water Vapor (Hygrometer)	Comment:	
5.	Turbulence Probe	Comment:	
6.	Altitude (RadarAlt)	Comment:	
7.	Doppler Radar	Comment:	
8.	Dropsonde (AVAPS)	Comment:	10 sondes launched - 1 had no wind data.

Radiation

9.	Broadband Radiometer (BBR)	Comment:	
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10.	Spectral Radiometer (ARIES)	Comment:	
11.	In-flight Microwave Obs System (DEIMOS)	Comment:	
12.	Microwave Radiometer Scanning System (MARSS)	Comment:	
13.	Shortwave Spectrometer (SWS)	Comment:	
14.	Spectral Irradiance (SHIM)	Comment:	lower SHIMS shutter half open - data should be ok
15.	Heimann Downward-facing Radiometer	Comment:	

Chemistry

16.	Ozone (CAMP 2B)	Comment:	Ozone data looks too low
17.	NO _x	Comment:	
18.	CO (AL5002)	Comment:	
19.	SO ₂ (TECO 43C)	Comment:	
20.	Sample Bottles (WAS)	Comment:	not carried in VOCALS
21.	CH ₄ /CO ₂ (NIR-TDLAS)	Comment:	
22.	PAN (GC)	Comment:	not operated
23.	Volatile Aerosol Composition (VACC)	Comment:	
24.	CH ₄ /N ₂ O (1C-TDLAS)	Comment:	

Cloud Physics and Aerosol

25.	Liquid and Total water probe	Comment:	
26.	LWC (Johnson Williams)	Comment:	
27.	TWC	Comment:	
28.	FFSSP	Comment:	
29.	2D-C	Comment:	
30.	PCASP	Comment:	anomalous high counts observed. Needs investigation.
31.	Small Ice Detector (SID-2)	Comment:	not fitted
32.	Cloud and Precipitation Imager (CIP-15)	Comment:	needs alignment
33.	Cloud Droplet Probe (CDP)	Comment:	
34.	Condensation Nucleus Counter (CNC)	Comment:	
35.	Cloud Condensation Nuclei Spectrometer (CCNc)	Comment:	only 1 channel working
36.	Fluorescence water vapour sensor (FWVS)	Comment:	
37.	Dry Nephelometer	Comment:	
38.	Wet Nephelometer	Comment:	
39.	Black Carbon (PSAP)	Comment:	
40.	Filters	Comment:	
41.	Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS)	Comment:	
42.	Counter-flow virtual Impactor (CVI)	Comment:	

43.	2-D Imaging Probe (SPEC-2D-S-128H)	Comment:	
44.	CAPS	Comment:	
45.	Single Particle Soot Photometer (SP-2)	Comment:	not fitted
46.	Fine-mode Aerosol Spectrometer (UHSAS)	Comment:	not fitted
47.	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS)	Comment:	down for this flight
48.	Ultrafine particle counter 1 (LP-WUCPC-1)	Comment:	
49.	Ultrafine particle counter 2 (LP-WUCPC-2)	Comment:	

Other

50.	SATCOM C	Comment:	
51.	SATCOM H	Comment:	
52.	Up, Down, Front, Rear Digital Imagery	Comment:	

[prev](#) | [next](#)

 [Back to VOCALS Field Catalog](#) | [edit](#) | [delete](#)

comments : gstoss at ucar.edu

Chemistry Log

Date: 5/11/08 Flight: B415 Operator: KT.
 Preflight CO, O₃, NO_x, SO₂ operated.

No. ? or x	Location	Action	Comments
Gases			
1	☒ CO2/Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
2	☒ CO2/Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi	172
3	☒ CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
4	☒ CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	44
5	☒ Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
6	☒ Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	30
Flows			
7	☒ Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 0.7 LPM on both channels	
8	☒ NOx sample flow	~ 1 LPM	
9	☒ NOx Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM	
10	☒ CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min	
11	☒ CO cell pressure	~ 7.5 bar	
12	☒ CO Pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar	
Zeros			
13	☒ Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	~ -0.3
14	☒ NOx zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	0.04, 0.19, 0.24
15	☒ CO zero	Left for approx 10 min	
Other			
16	☒ Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected	
17	☒ HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded	
18	☒ CO calibration <i>CO check set</i>	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)	
TDLAS			
19	☒ 230V	230V power breakers on	
20	☒ 28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)	
21	☒ Laptop	On and software working	
22	☒ Data	Being saved to correct directories	
Post Flight			
Switch off			
1	☒ CO	Switch off instrument	
2	☒ Ozone	Switch off monitor	
3	☒ NOx	Switch off monitor	
4	☒ Pumps	Switch off all pumps	
5	☒ Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP	
Gases (note pressures)			
6	☒ CO2/Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	175
7	☒ CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	45
8	☒ Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling	22
Driers			
9	☒ Small drier	Change if spent	<i>Change both</i>
10	☒ Large drier	Change if spent	
TDLAS			
11	☒ Data transfer	To memory stick	
12	☒ Laptop	Shut down	
13	☒ Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on	
Log			
14	☐ Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)	
15	☐ Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder	
16	☒ TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC	

Chemistry Log

In flight **B415**

CO calibrations only need carrying out when the lamp temperature changes, if unsure perform a quick cal first.

During each CO calibration check Ozone and NOx flows are similar to those observed pre-flight

Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)
09:10	Taxy	95.11	302	28732	40.25	7.52
Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)
Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)

VOCALS Core Chemistry Calibrations log

CO 'Cal' **B415**

Flight level	Zero Start	Zero End	Counts (Hz)	Span Start	Span End	Conc. Range	Counts range	Sensitivity	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	Lamp Temp	O3 Intensities Cell B
Taxy					09:10			95.11	302	28732	7.52	40.25	124492
FL200	09:40:00												
FL220	09:41:00	09:41:42	27758	09:42:00	09:42:30	495	74976		62	34276	7.50	40.48	
1400PT	11:19:45	-10ppb	27800			492	75900	—	—	—	7.53	39.52	110662
3300PT	12:57:20	-10ppb	27800			500	76500	—	—	—	7.54	38.41	110777
FL230	13:40:25	-11ppb	27410	13:41:10	13:42:12	505	76995	—	—	—	7.37	39.35	111470

In flight comments

Cap on FL180 09:27
 #1310 - checked pump - OK

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 415

Date: 05/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
07:20:00	U/S															17 micron bead cal	
09:16:13			1													FL040	
09:17:24																FL050	
09:18:34																FL060	
09:19:40			2													FL070	
09:20:28																FL080	
09:21:26																FL090	
09:22:20																FL100	
09:26:50																FL150	
09:31:40																FL200	
09:33:55																End of Profile 1 & Start Run 1 @ FL220	
09:40:00																	
09:50:00																	
10:00:00																	
10:10:00			3														
10:20:00																	
10:30:00																	
10:40:16																End of Run 1	
10:46:40	Neph	BS														Start Profile 2 from FL100	
10:48:35	1		3													FL080	
10:49:33	1															FL070	
10:50:41	2															FL060	
10:51:51	2		4													FL050	
10:52:49	2															FL040	
10:55:26																End of Profile 2 & Start Run 2 @ 2000'	
10:56:00	2		67														
10:58:00	4																
11:00:00	11																
11:02:00																End of Run 2	
11:03:53																Start Run 3 @ 2000'	
11:04:00	7																
11:06:00	6		68														
11:08:00	5																
11:10:00	5																
11:12:00	3																
11:14:00	2																
11:16:00	12					10	275								1		
11:18:00	1															Drop to 1500'	
11:20:00	7					10	300								1		
11:22:00	30		69			30	500								1	Drop 1000'	
11:24:00	4		70														
11:26:00	6		71			3	600								1		
11:28:00	6		72														

PCASP Reference Volts = n/a	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = n/a		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 415

Date: 05/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 3
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G.M.T	Neph BS		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
11:30:00	2		72														
11:31:24																End of Run	
11:32:51	2															Start Run Profile 3 from 1000'	
11:34:01	3					1										FL020	
11:34:55	10		83			2		60	20			0.5	50	28	0.45	FL030	
11:36:27	2		100													End of Profile 3 @ FL047	
11:37:59																Start Run 3 @ FL047	
11:38:00	3																
11:40:00	1																
11:42:11																End of Run	
11:43:39																Start Run 4 @ FL033	
11:46:00	4		216			4		100	18			0.4	100	20	0.3	12	
11:48:00	2		288			2	125	110	22			0.3	60	25	0.4	12	
11:50:00	2		383			15	25	50	28			0.3	40	30	0.3	12	
11:52:00	1		432			110	150	50	28			0.4	20	35	0.3	12	
11:55:00	1		475			600	250	50	32			0.6	50	32	0.8	1	
11:57:00	2		526			900	225	30	32			0.4	10	45	0.2	1	
11:59:00	1		546			700	275	40	30			0.6	30	32	0.6	1	
12:01:00	1		604			9	100	70	30			0.4	60	22	0.4	1	
12:05:00	1		818			3	75	160	20			0.35	100	20	0.35	12	
12:07:00	1		960			6	100	180	18			0.3	100	17	0.2	12	
12:09:00	1		1130			2		260	10			0.2	250	12	0.2		
12:11:00	1		1279			4	100	250	12			0.25	110	13	0.15	12	
12:14:24																End of Run & Start Profile 4	
12:15:13	2		1571													FL040	
12:17:45	1															End of Profile 4 @ FL063	
12:20:18	1															Start Profile 4 from FL063	
12:21:45	1															FL050	
12:22:47	1		1584			1		180	20			0.6	100	20	0.4	FL040	
12:23:48	2		1633													FL030	
12:24:39	1															FL020	
12:25:44	4															FL010	
12:27:56	8															End of Profile 4 & Start Profile 5 from 50'	
12:29:44	6															FL010	
12:30:48	4															FL020	
12:31:42	5		1659			4	125	90	20			0.5	100	20	0.5	12	
12:32:38	2															FL040	
12:33:45	2															FL050	
12:35:06	6															End of Profile 5 & Start Profile6 FL063	
12:36:31	1															FL050	
12:37:23	1															FL040	
12:38:23	1		1723			30	100	20	30			0.7	40	30	0.5	12	
12:39:25	1															FL020	

PCASP Reference Volts = n/a	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = n/a		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 415

Date: 05/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	Neph BS		FFSSP Block TX	SID1 Count	SID2 Count	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R				Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
12:40:27	1		1724													FL010	
12:43:19	2					6	500									End of Profile 6 & Start Profile 7 from 50'	
12:44:35	4		1725													FL010	
12:45:32	2															FL020	
12:46:13	3		1736													FL030	
12:47:02	2					300	200	50	30			0.6	30	32	0.5	FL040	
12:48:21	2		1750													FL050	
12:49:14																End of Profile 7	
12:50:52																Start Run 5 @ 3500'	
12:51:00	1		1770			1300	275	5	32			0.4	5	45	0.4	1	
12:53:00	1		1803			980	400	34	10			0.3	10	40	0.2	1	
12:55:54																End of Run 5	
12:57:18																Start Profile 8	
12:58:28			1863													FL020	
12:59:21																FL010	
13:02:10	1		1864													End of Profile 8 & Start Profile 9	
13:03:17																FL010	
13:03:31																Start Run 7 @ 1500'	
13:04:00	1																
13:06:00	1																
13:08:00	1																
13:10:00	1																
13:12:00	1																
13:13:26																End of Run 7 & Start P10	
13:14:06	1															FL020	
13:14:53	1		1893			10	125	150	20			0.5	150	20	0.6	12	
13:16:15	1		1918													FL030	
13:17:20	1															FL050	
13:17:33	1															FL060	
13:17:33	1															FL070	
13:18:47	1															FL080	
13:18:56	2															FL090	
13:19:25	1															FL100	
13:22:33	1															FL150	
13:28:57	1															End of P10 & Start Run 8 @ FL230	
14:09:23																End of Run 8 & Start Profile 11	
	PCASP U/S																

PCASP Reference Volts = n/a	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V
PCASP Flow rate = n/a		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a	

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B415	Date	05/11/2008	Operator	KFT	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
094000	1	Launch	427.00 -12.40 7.14 240.40 16.30 0.50 -72.412100 -18.833500 6720.00
094855	1	Splashdown	1013.58 17.42 70.35 153.98 4.17 -10.42 -72.391676 -18.834661
			Parachute repacked before launching sensor end first.
095504	2	Launch	425.51 9.16 1.09 999.00 999.00 99.00 999.000000 99.000000 6979.33
100021	2	Splashdown	1010.98 16.20 73.15 999.00 999.00 99.00 999.000000 99.000000 -109.21
			Parachute repacked before launching sensor end first. No GPS. No launch detect.
101642	3	Launch	427.10 -12.40 4.03 253.40 13.30 0.40 -75.525000 -19.462200 6718.70
102532	3	Splashdown	1007.59 15.62 64.93 141.56 7.42 -8.89 -75.486233 -19.467239 -298.27
			Parachute repacked before launching sensor end first.
102503	4	Launch	427.30 -13.00 4.05 263.30 14.80 0.60 -76.232500 -19.623900 6716.30
103023	4	Splashdown	1012.17 15.29 66.91 156.72 4.55 -19.82 -76.210208 -19.627457 99999.00
			Parachute repacked before launching sensor end first.
104003	5	Launch	427.30 -13.10 4.08 255.90 16.40 0.50 -77.470400 -19.885300 6715.20
104833	5	Splashdown	1008.85 14.56 74.08 156.47 8.81 -11.22 -77.432451 -19.885478 -295.14
			Parachute repacked before launching sensor end first.
133203	6	Launch	409.40 -15.40 4.35 246.60 11.00 0.30 -75.607500 -19.110700 7020.30
134056	6	Splashdown	1004.67 15.42 68.81 136.64 5.45 -12.78 -75.575888 -19.116064 -296.37
			Parachute repacked before launching sensor end first.
133903	7	Launch	409.10 -15.20 4.19 260.20 8.80 0.30 -74.914400 -19.079300 7025.60
134747	7	Splashdown	1004.54 15.82 73.93 169.45 5.08 -13.91 -74.883407 -19.082469 -297.78
			Parachute repacked before launching sensor end first.
134706	8	Launch	410.00 -15.00 6.27 248.80 8.40 0.40 -74.133500 -18.996900 7009.30
135613	8	Splashdown	1003.50 16.29 71.06 163.43 4.08 -10.39 -74.105770 -19.001808 -296.77
			Parachute repacked before launching sensor end first.
135412	9	Launch	409.20 -15.10 6.53 249.10 8.60 0.30 -73.452900 -18.927500 7023.80
140256	9	Splashdown	1003.80 16.54 74.76 149.05 3.61 -9.55 -73.440225 -18.934698 -296.90
			Parachute repacked before launching sensor end first.
140103	10	Launch	409.40 -14.90 6.78 252.30 6.00 0.40 -72.797600 -18.872600 7020.20
140949	10	Splashdown	1002.90 16.47 71.24 173.25 2.72 -11.36 -72.775195 -18.875086 -297.03
			Parachute repacked before launching sensor end first.

size	#	charged	Flight/dale	discharged	comments
10	1	4/11			
1	2	KWB	NOT USED	S/11	
10	3	4/11			
1	4	KWB	NOT USED	/	
10	7	3/11	B415	S/11	
1	8	KWB	S/11/08	KWB	
10	10	4/11	B415	S/11	
1	69	KWB	S/11/08	KWB	
10	21	3/11			
1	23	KWB	NOT USED	/	
10	33	3/11	B415	S/11	
1	40	KWB	S/11/08	KWB	

filter # Loc'n Ton Toff Kun Vol

Flight:

B415

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:
 Heimann:
 Deiced Temp:
 Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:
 Buck CR2:
 General Eastern:
 Johnson Williams:
 Nevzorov:
 Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:
 Forward Facing:
 Rearward Facing:
 Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:
 GIN Applanix:
 INU Honeywell:
 Radar Altimeter:
 RVSM IAS:
 RVSM Static Pressure:
 XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:
 AMTG:
 AVAPS:
 Cabin Pressure:
 Printer:
 S9 Static Pressure:
 Satcom C:
 Satcom H (VIRC):
 Turb Centre-Static:
 Turb Left Right:
 Turb Up-Down:
 Turb Horizontal Chk:
 Turb Vertical Chk:
 Weather Radar:
DLUs:
 DLU AERACK:
 DLU BBR Lower:
 DLU BBR Upper:
 DLU Core Chem:
 DLU Core Consoles:
 DLU Port Aft:
 DLU Port Fwd:
 DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:
 BBR (clear) Lower:
 BBR (IR) Lower:
 BBR (red) Lower:
Upper:
 BBR (clear) Upper:
 BBR (IR) Upper:
 BBR (red) Upper:
 ARIES:
 DEIMOS:
 IR Camera:
 JNO2 Lower:
 JNO2 Upper:
 JO1D Lower:
 JO1D Upper:
 MARSS:
 SHIMS Lower:
 SHIMS Upper:
 SWS:
 TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:
 2DP:
 FFSSP:
 PCASP:
 PCASP SPP-200:
 2DS:
 ADA:
 CAPS:
 CCN:
 CDP (fuselage):
 CDP (Canister):
 CIP 100 (PIP):
 CIP 25 (CIP):
 CPI:
 CVI (Inlet):
 CVI PCASP-X:
 CVI Ly-A Hygro:
 FSSP (UMan):
 SID1:
 SID2:
 SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:
 CPC 3786 H2O:
 Filters 47mm:
 Filters 90mm:
 Neph - Dry:
 Neph - Wet:
 PSAP:
 AMS:
 CPC (AMS):
 SMPS (AMS):
 CPC 3010A (CVI):
 INC:
 Mini-LIDAR:
 SP2:
 UHSAS:
 VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:
 NOx TE42C:
 Ozone TE49C:
 Ozone TE49:
 SO2 TE43C:
 TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
 TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
 FAGE:
 Formaldehyde:
 NOx FAAM:
 NOxy:
 ORAC:
 PAN:
 PERCA:
 Peroxide:
 PTRMS:
 TDLAS (1C):
 WAS Bags:
 WAS Bottles:
Misc Non-Core
 CASI/ATM:
 LIDAR (big):
 LTI:
 SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B415

Date: 05/11/08

Instruments

RFC	condensation running on inside of window
Drosondes	4 dropped, 1 sonde did not lock to GPS or get a launch detect
Core Chem -	Low ozone values?
Cloud physics -	PCASP – still evidence of a leak
ARIES -	computer crashed once, recovered ok
CCN -	single channel only
VACC -	minor CPC fault
2DS -	one crash, reset ok
Buck -	experimental operation ->ok

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

MPDS

Run for flight

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Issues

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 05/11/08

Flight No: B 415

Pre-Flighter: Mo

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	- Kate
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☐	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	KT
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☐	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	KT
5	☐	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	KT
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	☐	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	Status 4088 (TDET not set)
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	N/A

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	UIS
26	☒	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	JB
27	☒	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	JB
28	☒	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	UIS
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☒	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
41	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	☒	Upper BBRs	Checked & Cleaned	Signed a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
45	☒	ICEX	applied	
46	☒	Turb Probe - Traps	emptied, detail contents -	
47	☒	Turb Probe - Traps	dried and resealed	

CVI log

11/5/08 7:29:14 AM noise in lower pcasp chn
11/5/08 7:31:39 AM lylamp=0.26
11/5/08 7:31:50 AM correction lylamp=0.16
11/5/08 7:36:54 AM correction lylamp=0.16
11/5/08 7:36:57 AM correction lylamp=0.16
11/5/08 7:37:01 AM correction lylamp=0.16
11/5/08 7:37:13 AM correction lylamp=0.16
11/5/08 7:38:51 AM good zero of pcasp with counterflow on
11/5/08 7:39:15 AM good zero of pcasp with counterflow on
11/5/08 7:39:18 AM good zero of pcasp with counterflow on
11/5/08 7:39:27 AM good zero of pcasp with counterflow on
11/5/08 7:42:22 AM good zero of pcasp with counterflow on
11/5/08 7:43:25 AM good zero of pcasp with counterflow on
11/5/08 7:45:18 AM shook dririte - indicator is >90% blue (ok)
11/5/08 7:47:50 AM pids set to tip=25,sample=45,cf=45
11/5/08 8:31:18 AM lyman zeroed
11/5/08 8:31:25 AM pcasp now has data stream
11/5/08 8:31:32 AM counterflow is set to 5 for take off
11/5/08 8:31:44 AM lyman valve is set to sample
11/5/08 8:31:51 AM counterflow valve is open
11/5/08 8:32:04 AM horace feed is ok
11/5/08 8:32:17 AM try to get counterflow low enough to sample more of the cluod
11/5/08 8:43:44 AM ano
11/5/08 8:43:53 AM ano
11/5/08 8:48:24 AM lyman back on counterflow air
11/5/08 8:56:16 AM drop counterflow temp to 40
11/5/08 8:56:29 AM pid measuring 56
11/5/08 9:21:04 AM going to startm too high for pcasp and CVI in general
11/5/08 9:23:06 AM going to startm too high for pcasp and CVI in general
11/5/08 9:23:14 AM going to startm too high for pcasp and CVI in general
11/5/08 9:23:17 AM going to startm too high for pcasp and CVI in general
11/5/08 9:25:18 AM temp light flashing on cpc. sat=35, cond=20
11/5/08 9:29:16 AM zero lyman alpha
11/5/08 9:29:56 AM reduce counterflow
11/5/08 9:31:05 AM reduce counterflow
11/5/08 9:31:45 AM wavelength invariant scattering = large paricles on neph - dust?
11/5/08 9:32:03 AM l control=2 at 6200m gives a zero
11/5/08 9:33:00 AM counterflow removed from probe
11/5/08 9:33:10 AM dry bair now goes to lyman only
11/5/08 9:38:43 AM cpc counts compare well with cpc on VACC
11/5/08 9:38:59 AM pcasp concs are very low - flow at altitude?
11/5/08 9:52:09 AM cpc concs still high at 6700m
11/5/08 9:53:16 AM pcasp almost zero
11/5/08 9:53:36 AM lyman alpha - in the noise - TWC reports 1.1g/kg
11/5/08 9:54:35 AM lyman alpha - in the noise - TWC reports 1.1g/kg
11/5/08 9:54:39 AM lyman alpha - in the noise - TWC reports 1.1g/kg
11/5/08 9:54:46 AM lyman alpha - in the noise - TWC reports 1.1g/kg
11/5/08 10:08:33 AM lyman alpha - in the noise - TWC reports 1.1g/kg
11/5/08 10:08:51 AM lyman alpha - in the noise - TWC reports 1.1g/kg
11/5/08 10:09:54 AM fall in CPC - is this real or is this because we banked to
collect the sonde
11/5/08 10:13:27 AM fall in CPC - is this real or is this because we banked to
collect the sonde
11/5/08 10:14:29 AM did cpc drop off at the coastal boundary
11/5/08 10:20:16 AM looks like a real signal - 500 down to 373
11/5/08 10:27:52 AM some structure to cpc counts two blips
11/5/08 10:27:58 AM same on the cn rack
11/5/08 10:31:28 AM swap lyman sample flow just to check!
11/5/08 10:33:08 AM put lyman back to sample from plenum - no change!
11/5/08 10:33:49 AM fall off in cpc to 337
11/5/08 10:34:22 AM fall off in cpc to 337
11/5/08 10:34:29 AM fall off in cpc to 337
11/5/08 10:39:11 AM fall off in cpc to 337
11/5/08 10:40:21 AM fall off in cpc to 337
11/5/08 10:40:24 AM fall off in cpc to 337
11/5/08 10:40:34 AM fall off in cpc to 337
11/5/08 10:43:20 AM fall off in cpc to 337

11/5/08 10:43:22 AM fall off in cpc to 337
11/5/08 10:47:28 AM fall off in cpc to 337
11/5/08 10:47:31 AM fall off in cpc to 337
11/5/08 10:47:36 AM fall off in cpc to 337
11/5/08 10:48:00 AM profile descent leave in aerosol mode, just to pass through cloud
and do sub cloud run
11/5/08 10:48:06 AM cpc counts dropping
11/5/08 10:48:51 AM 8000ft cpc=200,
11/5/08 10:48:52 AM 8000ft cpc=200,
11/5/08 10:48:56 AM 8000ft cpc=200,
11/5/08 10:49:08 AM cpc counts increasing now
11/5/08 10:52:17 AM adjust pcasp flow for new altitude
11/5/08 10:52:39 AM adjust pcasp flow for new altitude
11/5/08 10:53:06 AM in cloud top
11/5/08 10:53:39 AM lycwc is now climbing
11/5/08 10:54:43 AM lycwc still coming through
11/5/08 10:57:01 AM some drizzle around
11/5/08 10:57:15 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 10:57:26 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 10:57:31 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 10:57:33 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 10:57:36 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 10:57:39 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 10:57:43 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 10:57:47 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 10:57:50 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 10:57:52 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 11:00:55 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 11:00:58 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 11:01:01 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 11:01:07 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 11:01:47 AM lycwc now higher, 5.0
11/5/08 11:02:12 AM turning
11/5/08 11:03:58 AM turning
11/5/08 11:08:06 AM turning
11/5/08 11:10:04 AM turning
11/5/08 11:10:13 AM turning
11/5/08 11:13:28 AM turning
11/5/08 11:13:37 AM turning
11/5/08 11:13:42 AM turning
11/5/08 11:15:33 AM turning
11/5/08 11:15:36 AM turning
11/5/08 11:16:39 AM turning
11/5/08 11:17:16 AM we have just left a MASSIVE spike
11/5/08 11:18:36 AM we have just left a MASSIVE spike
11/5/08 11:18:44 AM we have just left a MASSIVE spike
11/5/08 11:18:47 AM we have just left a MASSIVE spike
11/5/08 11:18:51 AM we have just left a MASSIVE spike
11/5/08 11:21:10 AM drizzle? dropping altitude now
11/5/08 11:21:32 AM heavy drizzle
11/5/08 11:21:46 AM shattering?
11/5/08 11:21:59 AM shattering?
11/5/08 11:22:06 AM shattering?
11/5/08 11:23:31 AM so are we not heating enough, to evaporate the drops so they
shatter in the probe, and the
11/5/08 11:23:49 AM lycwc didnt increase during the drizzle,
11/5/08 11:24:44 AM turning up tip heater to 30 deg
11/5/08 11:25:29 AM drizzle at 600microns, bigger, 49li1
11/5/08 11:25:33 AM drizzle at 600microns, bigger, 49li1
11/5/08 11:25:34 AM drizzle at 600microns, bigger, 49li1
11/5/08 11:25:39 AM 40 per litre
11/5/08 11:26:00 AM shattering again
11/5/08 11:27:06 AM shattering again
11/5/08 11:31:51 AM end of run 3 climbing to cloud leg
11/5/08 11:32:05 AM will pop above cloud to zero cvi before dropping back down
11/5/08 11:33:30 AM will pop above cloud to zero cvi before dropping back down
11/5/08 11:34:12 AM messing with total sample flow - idea set AMD flow negative to
overcome the offset of the counterflow flow control at zero counterflow
11/5/08 11:35:31 AM shattering again, noise on cpc

11/5/08 11:35:42 AM water coming through on lycwc
11/5/08 11:35:49 AM not much though
11/5/08 11:36:58 AM into counterflow mode
11/5/08 11:37:30 AM trp 0.6 l control at 1137
11/5/08 11:37:58 AM trp 0.6 l control at 1137
11/5/08 11:38:03 AM trp 0.6 l control at 1137
11/5/08 11:38:08 AM trp 0.6 l control at 1137
11/5/08 11:38:34 AM trp 0.6 l control at 1137
11/5/08 11:38:44 AM set ams flow to -0.2
11/5/08 11:39:25 AM reduce l control
11/5/08 11:40:17 AM cf=1.3 if offset is 0.5 then cf=2.0
11/5/08 11:40:26 AM sample = 1.0+0.5+0.7
11/5/08 11:43:19 AM in cloud NOW
11/5/08 11:43:29 AM in cloud NOWcpc increases massively
11/5/08 11:43:41 AM pcasp increases massively
11/5/08 11:43:46 AM pcasp increases massively
11/5/08 11:44:15 AM initial spike in paricles then a drop
11/5/08 11:44:23 AM lwc~0.05
11/5/08 11:44:32 AM lwc~0.05
11/5/08 11:44:45 AM lwc~0.05
11/5/08 11:44:49 AM lwc~0.05
11/5/08 11:44:53 AM lwc~0.05
11/5/08 11:47:36 AM lots of counts on pcasp below 1 micron
11/5/08 11:48:18 AM cloud base popped out
11/5/08 11:49:25 AM reduce L control to 0.2
11/5/08 11:49:49 AM reduce L control to 0.2
11/5/08 11:50:00 AM reduce L control to 0.2
11/5/08 11:50:10 AM reduce L control to 0.2
11/5/08 11:50:40 AM bright above
11/5/08 11:52:39 AM drop concs increasing
11/5/08 11:53:15 AM lwc 0.2g/m3
11/5/08 11:53:47 AM we seem to be seeing about half the liquid water
11/5/08 11:54:03 AM we seem to be seeing about half the liquid water
11/5/08 11:55:16 AM raw cpc counts are about 14000, very high
11/5/08 11:55:25 AM lwc just increased
11/5/08 11:56:14 AM hole in cloud
11/5/08 11:56:22 AM hole in cloud below
11/5/08 11:56:28 AM 200ft thick#
11/5/08 11:57:04 AM seeing significant aerosol as well as cloud
11/5/08 11:57:18 AM cas ends up with suppressed cloud radius as a result
11/5/08 11:57:44 AM cas ends up with suppressed cloud radius as a result
11/5/08 11:58:02 AM cas ends up with suppressed cloud radius as a result
11/5/08 11:58:40 AM cas ends up with suppressed cloud radius as a result
11/5/08 11:59:47 AM concentrastions all falling off
11/5/08 12:01:03 PM reduce counterflow again for last section of run and risk aerosol
11/5/08 12:03:10 PM reduce counterflow again for last section of run and risk aerosol
11/5/08 12:03:18 PM macFSSP=120
11/5/08 12:03:20 PM macFSSP=120
11/5/08 12:03:26 PM cdp a bit higher
11/5/08 12:03:53 PM cdp a bit higher
11/5/08 12:04:03 PM cdp a bit higher
11/5/08 12:04:36 PM smell butanol
11/5/08 12:05:57 PM smell butanol
11/5/08 12:07:52 PM increas l control back to 0.2
11/5/08 12:09:55 PM reduce counterflow to 0.1 again
11/5/08 12:15:33 PM above cloud top now, counts falling
11/5/08 12:16:35 PM above cloud top now, counts falling
11/5/08 12:16:47 PM ams back to rosemount
11/5/08 12:16:57 PM reduce ams flow to -0.6
11/5/08 12:18:26 PM ams staying on rosemount for the saw tooth
11/5/08 12:18:52 PM ams staying on rosemount for the saw tooth
11/5/08 12:19:15 PM reduce ams flow to -0.7 to attempt to correct the counterflow
balance
11/5/08 12:22:52 PM in cloud on the waydown
11/5/08 12:23:28 PM in cloud on the waydown
11/5/08 12:23:37 PM in cloud on the waydown
11/5/08 12:25:54 PM try and operate in/out of cvi mode when in/out of cloud
11/5/08 12:26:16 PM change over at the bottom
11/5/08 12:26:59 PM counterflow is off

11/5/08 12:27:54 PM 50ft
11/5/08 12:28:01 PM 50ft
11/5/08 12:29:16 PM 50ft
11/5/08 12:29:19 PM 50ft
11/5/08 12:29:22 PM 50ft
11/5/08 12:29:24 PM 50ft
11/5/08 12:29:33 PM 50ft
11/5/08 12:29:36 PM 50ft
11/5/08 12:29:39 PM 50ft
11/5/08 12:31:43 PM cloud base 3.1kft
11/5/08 12:32:20 PM cloud top 4000
11/5/08 12:32:32 PM in aerosol mode for that cloud passgae
11/5/08 12:39:25 PM in aerosol mode for that cloud passgae
11/5/08 12:39:34 PM in aerosol mode for that cloud passgae
11/5/08 12:39:37 PM in aerosol mode for that cloud passgae
11/5/08 12:39:41 PM in aerosol mode for that cloud passgae
11/5/08 12:39:48 PM in aerosol mode for that cloud passgae
11/5/08 12:40:03 PM in aerosol mode for that cloud passgae
11/5/08 12:42:36 PM pcasp layer
11/5/08 12:44:04 PM counts just increased massivley - drizzle reported by MS1
11/5/08 12:45:10 PM flow to cpc will remain the same
11/5/08 12:45:21 PM flow to cpc will remain the same
11/5/08 12:45:30 PM flow to cpc will remain the same
11/5/08 12:46:33 PM sub cloud structure, drizzle, evaporates sub cloud above surface
ca
11/5/08 12:46:37 PM sub cloud structure, drizzle, evaporates sub cloud above surface
ca
11/5/08 12:46:50 PM causes drop in temperature, increase in humidity,
11/5/08 12:47:05 PM eventual decoupling, layer below cloud
11/5/08 12:49:11 PM run in cloud
11/5/08 12:49:54 PM ams on cvi
11/5/08 12:50:03 PM cvi mode now
11/5/08 12:50:23 PM in cloud
11/5/08 12:50:42 PM in cloud
11/5/08 12:50:53 PM run start
11/5/08 12:51:16 PM cpc=100, pcasp=54
11/5/08 12:52:11 PM cpc=100, pcasp=54
11/5/08 12:53:46 PM much higher concss than cloud physics
11/5/08 12:53:55 PM must be lots of drizzle shattering
11/5/08 12:54:04 PM cloud phys say there is some
11/5/08 12:54:13 PM lwc=0.4
11/5/08 12:54:23 PM
11/5/08 12:56:04 PM end of run,
11/5/08 12:56:18 PM go back to aerosol mode
11/5/08 12:58:11 PM cf off NOW
11/5/08 12:58:20 PM profile decent
11/5/08 12:58:27 PM cloud base about 3.5
11/5/08 12:58:36 PM correction 2.5
11/5/08 12:58:50 PM next sub cloud run at 1.5kft
11/5/08 12:59:35 PM
11/5/08 1:00:31 PM drizzle
11/5/08 1:02:47 PM very low pcasp
11/5/08 1:03:06 PM pcasp seem to follow ccn very closly in this region
11/5/08 1:03:46 PM pcasp seem to follow ccn very closly in this region
11/5/08 1:04:09 PM pcasp seem to follow ccn very closly in this region
11/5/08 1:04:17 PM pcasp seem to follow ccn very closly in this region
11/5/08 1:08:23 PM smell butanol
11/5/08 1:09:02 PM smell butanol
11/5/08 1:09:10 PM smell butanol
11/5/08 1:11:19 PM smell butanol
11/5/08 1:11:57 PM sulphate is now hig
11/5/08 1:12:12 PM aroud 1 microgram, up from nothing in the poc
11/5/08 1:21:20 PM much lower pcasp up high
11/5/08 1:24:21 PM much lower pcasp up high
11/5/08 1:24:39 PM much lower pcasp up high
11/5/08 1:24:47 PM much lower pcasp up high
11/5/08 1:25:36 PM adjust pcasp flows for high level
11/5/08 2:38:49 PM cvi in aerosol mode for last descent.
11/5/08 2:39:02 PM switch flow to reference to do a lyman zero

11/5/08 2:43:57 PM Lyman zero NOW
11/5/08 2:44:02 PM end

ARIES flight log

Flight: B415

page 1 of 2

Date: 05 Nov 2008 Operator(s): S. Rogers

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: VOCALS

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Fit ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
~0710	Power on						40 55
073045	—		CH	C	71	31	ColdHot/min. script 10 25
~0912	TAKE OFF		—		71	31	40
093550	FL220		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3min. script ^{Crabtree?}
094237	FL220		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3min ^{8/8 Sec below} _{Sound 1}
095235	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3min _{Sound 2}
095666	"		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3min
100640	"		Z	O	70	31	Zenith Long Run 3min ^{Script} _{Lock up @ 357/360}
101630	"		Z	O	71	30	Zenith Long Run 3min _{Sound 3}
101856	"		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3min
102150	"		Z	O	71	30	Zenith Long Run 3min _{Sound 4}
102606	"		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3min
103802	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3min _{Sound 5}
104024	"		CH	C	70	31	ColdHot/min
105528	^{R2} 2000 ft		NZ	O	71	30	Nad Zen Long Run 30sec. _{Under 8/8 Sec}
1102				O	70	31	Banking
110348	^{R3} 2000ft						
111655	↓			O	71	31	Easy down to 1500ft
							HE has locked up mid-script.
							'top' shows 129% GPU usage
1125							Restart of system OK.
112611	1500ft?		N	C	71	35	Nadir Long Run 3min. script
113628	1500ft?		N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3min until 11:42
121750	↓						Going down to 50ft
122555	↓		N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3min
1234	↑↓		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30sec _{to 12:38}
124614	↑		NZ	O	71	31	— " —
124909	6000ft						Banking
125229			NZ	O	72	30	Nad Zen Long Run 30sec
130525	^{R7} 1500ft			O	70	31	
131332	Plot			C	71	31	

B415_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

09:16:01.59 --- - - - -
09:16:01.60 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:16:01.60 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:16:01.60 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B415
09:16:01.60 --- - - - -
09:16:28.97 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
09:16:31.58 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
09:16:36.80 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:16:40.62 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:16:43.51 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:16:46.16 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:16:46.25 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:16:46.43 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:16:59.86 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:17:02.47 SWS - - 600 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
09:17:02.47 SWS - - - 600 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
09:17:04.13 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:17:07.96 USH - - 600 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
09:17:07.97 USH - - - 600 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
09:17:09.39 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:17:12.71 LSH - - 600 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
09:17:12.72 LSH - - - 600 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
09:17:14.30 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:17:14.30 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:17:14.31 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:17:17.66 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:17:23.59 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:17:23.69 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:17:23.95 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:17:30.03 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:17:30.25 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:17:30.43 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:17:53.27 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:17:53.50 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:17:53.71 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:17:59.72 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:17:59.95 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:18:00.14 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:18:03.66 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:18:03.90 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:18:04.09 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:18:10.38 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:18:10.41 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:18:11.02 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:18:13.07 USH - - - - Idling
09:18:13.09 LSH - - - - Idling
09:18:13.27 SWS - - - - Idling
09:20:50.42 --- - - - - *** 16 deg
09:30:07.39 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:30:07.39 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:30:07.40 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:30:13.11 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:30:17.98 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:30:18.14 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:30:18.60 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:30:24.43 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:30:24.63 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:30:25.67 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:30:32.95 --- - - - - *** 15 deg
09:34:20.48 --- - - - - *** end of profile climb
09:40:01.46 --- - - - - *** sonde 1
09:42:08.36 --- - - - - *** 15 degree
09:42:36.43 --- - - - - *** sun is beggining to rise
09:42:44.07 --- - - - - *** 16 deg
09:45:13.41 --- - - - - *** 15 deg
09:55:02.47 --- - - - - *** sonde 2

```

09:55:47.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:47.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:48.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:49.96	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:55:58.29	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:56:05.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:05.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:05.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:12.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:12.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:12.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:15.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:15.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:15.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:21.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:22.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:22.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:25.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:25.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:25.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:31.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:31.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:32.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:45.39	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:56:47.07	SWS	171.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:56:49.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:49.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:49.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:57:36.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
09:58:59.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
10:01:30.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:01:51.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:01:51.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:01:52.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:01.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:01.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:01.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:08.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:08.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:08.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:10.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:10.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:10.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:16.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:16.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:17.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:19.01	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 40ms.
10:02:19.02	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 40ms.
10:02:23.03	USH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 40ms.
10:02:23.04	USH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 40ms.
10:02:27.94	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
10:02:27.94	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
10:02:30.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:30.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:30.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:32.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:32.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:32.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:34.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:34.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:34.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:35.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:35.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:36.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:39.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:39.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:39.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:40.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:40.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

10:02:41.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:42.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:42.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:42.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:43.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:43.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:44.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:48.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:02:48.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:02:48.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:19.33	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:03:25.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:25.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:25.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:26.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:26.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:27.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:28.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:28.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:28.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:29.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:29.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:30.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:32.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:32.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:32.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:32.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:33.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:33.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:06.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:06:52.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:06:52.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:06:52.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:06:54.09	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:06:55.77	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:07:12.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:12.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:12.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:13.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:14.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:14.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:15.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:15.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:15.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:16.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:16.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:17.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:19.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:19.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:19.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:20.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:20.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:21.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:27.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:27.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:27.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:46.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:08:12.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:10:10.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:12:14.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:16:42.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 3
10:20:17.67	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:20:21.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:21.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:21.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:26.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:26.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:26.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:27.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

10:20:27.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:28.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:28.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:28.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:28.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:29.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:30.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:30.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:31.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:31.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:31.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:32.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:33.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:33.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:34.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:34.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:34.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:35.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:36.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:36.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:42.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:42.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:42.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:48.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:48.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:48.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:49.88	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:20:51.57	SWS	173.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:20:53.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:53.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:53.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:14.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:22:24.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:23:35.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:23:35.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:23:35.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:23:38.87	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:23:40.57	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:23:57.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:23:57.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:23:57.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:23:58.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:23:59.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:23:59.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:01.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:01.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:01.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:02.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:02.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:02.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:03.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:03.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:03.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:04.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:04.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:05.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:05.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:05.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:05.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:07.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:07.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:07.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:19.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:19.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:19.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:02.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 4
10:25:43.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:26:11.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:11.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

10:26:11.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:23.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:23.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:23.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:23.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:24.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:24.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:25.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:25.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:25.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:26.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:27.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:27.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:28.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:28.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:28.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:28.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:29.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:29.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:37.45	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:26:39.13	SWS	172.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:26:43.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:43.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:43.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:03.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:29:24.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** patchy cirrus above
10:29:42.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** stratocumulus sheet below
10:32:47.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
10:37:30.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:31.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:31.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:33.00	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:37:34.67	SWS	-0.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:37:50.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:50.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:50.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:51.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:52.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:52.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:54.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:54.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:54.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:55.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:55.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:55.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:57.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:57.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:57.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:58.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:58.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:58.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:38:03.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:03.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:03.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:05.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** fairly extensive cirrus above
10:39:23.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** thick stratocumulus sheet below
10:40:01.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 5
10:40:21.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run a
10:40:32.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** and descending tp 5000 ft
10:40:39.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:40:40.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:40:40.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:40:45.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:45.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:45.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:46.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:46.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:46.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:47.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

10:40:47.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:48.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:49.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:49.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:49.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:50.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:50.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:51.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:51.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:51.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:51.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:52.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:53.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:53.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:53.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:53.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:53.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:54.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:54.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:55.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:56.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:56.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:56.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:57.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:57.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:57.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:59.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:59.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:59.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:00.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:00.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:01.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:07.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:07.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:07.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:09.41	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:41:11.10	SWS	171.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:41:15.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:15.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:15.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:55.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** getting breaks in stratq sheet below
10:46:42.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** point zulu
10:46:50.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending to 3000 ft
10:47:33.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 2
10:47:41.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 degree
10:53:11.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** entering cloud
10:54:17.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** leaving cloujd CT 3800 ft
10:54:30.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 3000 ft
10:54:38.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:55:27.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile
10:55:42.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 2000 ft
10:55:47.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 2
10:56:06.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:06.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:06.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:08.64	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:56:10.36	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:56:20.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:20.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:20.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:21.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:21.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:21.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:23.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:23.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:23.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:23.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:24.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:24.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

10:56:25.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:25.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:25.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:26.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:27.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:27.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:32.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:32.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:32.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:59.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
11:02:02.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
11:02:07.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning
11:02:27.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 2
11:03:51.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3
11:04:29.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
11:05:36.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:36.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:36.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:38.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:39.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:47.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:47.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:47.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:48.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:48.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:48.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:50.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:50.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:50.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:51.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:51.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:51.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:53.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:53.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:53.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:54.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:54.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:55.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:07.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:20.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
11:12:03.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
11:13:25.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
11:16:42.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** on boundary of POC region
11:17:15.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** seeing a large amount of variability in downwelling radiation on sws
11:17:48.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** easing down to 1500 ft
11:18:02.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** to avoid going into cloud
11:20:40.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
11:21:15.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** easing down to 1000 ft
11:21:38.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** heavy drizzle
11:27:26.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:26.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:26.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:29.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:32.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:37.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:42.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:42.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:42.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:42.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:43.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:43.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:46.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:46.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:46.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:47.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:47.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:47.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:50.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:27:50.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:50.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:51.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:51.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:52.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:00.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:00.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:15.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:29:43.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
11:31:24.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
11:31:31.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning
11:31:47.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing
11:32:52.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
11:34:55.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 3000 ft
11:35:06.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
11:35:42.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3900 ft
11:37:06.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
11:38:00.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
11:38:05.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 4900 ft
11:38:13.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:13.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:13.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:13.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:18.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:18.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:18.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:19.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:20.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:20.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:22.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:22.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:22.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:23.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:23.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:24.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:25.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:26.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:26.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:26.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:27.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:27.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:38:35.06	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:38:36.76	SWS	173.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:38:38.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:38.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:38.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:19.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending
11:42:48.47	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:42:50.24	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:43:18.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** cirrus above
11:43:34.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** stratq sheet below
11:43:48.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 3500 ft in cloud
11:43:55.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:55.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:55.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:01.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:01.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:01.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:02.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:02.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:02.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:03.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:03.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:03.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:04.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:05.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:05.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:06.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:06.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:44:06.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:07.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:07.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:08.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:13.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:44:13.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:44:13.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:44:26.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:49:14.18	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:49:15.93	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:51:24.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:52:32.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:53:23.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:23.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:23.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:26.38	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:53:28.10	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:53:35.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:35.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:35.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:36.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:37.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:37.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:38.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:38.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:38.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:39.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:39.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:40.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:42.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:42.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:42.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:43.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:44.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:44.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:51.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:51.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:51.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:44.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:00:08.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:08.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:08.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:14.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:14.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:14.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:15.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:15.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:16.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:17.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:17.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:17.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:18.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:18.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:18.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:19.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:19.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:21.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:21.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:21.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:22.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:22.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:22.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:30.92	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:00:32.64	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:00:34.10	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:00:39.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:00:39.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:00:39.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:54.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg

12:03:11.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:05:23.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:23.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:23.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:26.02	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:05:27.75	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:05:35.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:35.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:35.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:36.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:36.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:37.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:38.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:38.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:38.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:38.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:39.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:39.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:40.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:40.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:40.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:40.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:41.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:41.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:46.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:46.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:46.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:37.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:11:47.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:14:25.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run start of profile climb
12:15:22.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4100 ft
12:16:57.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:57.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:57.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:05.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:05.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:05.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:06.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:07.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:07.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:08.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:08.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:08.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:08.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:09.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:09.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:10.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:10.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:10.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:11.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:11.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:12.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:18.25	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:17:19.97	SWS	173.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:17:23.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:23.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:23.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:33.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
12:20:18.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** sawtooth profile descending to 50 ft
12:23:48.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** now below cloud
12:23:55.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:55.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:55.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:55.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:58.05	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:23:59.82	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:24:03.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:04.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:04.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

12:24:30.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:25:43.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** CT 4000 CB around 3100 ft
12:26:10.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** thats around 4000 ft for CT
12:27:56.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft reverse sawtooth
12:28:37.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 6
12:31:49.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 3100 ft
12:32:23.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4000 ft
12:32:28.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:33:14.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** cirus sheet above
12:33:35.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:35.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:35.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:45.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:45.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:45.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:46.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:46.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:46.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:47.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:47.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:47.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:48.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:48.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:49.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:49.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:49.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:49.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:50.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:50.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:51.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:55.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:33:56.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:33:56.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:33:59.50	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:34:01.23	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:34:33.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:35:06.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** reversing profile at 6500 ft
12:37:44.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4000 ft
12:38:13.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
12:39:11.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:11.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:11.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:15.22	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:39:16.95	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:39:22.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:22.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:22.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:23.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:24.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:24.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:25.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:25.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:25.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:26.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:26.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:27.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:27.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:27.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:27.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:28.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:28.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:29.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:34.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:34.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:34.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:41:20.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:41:31.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** drizzle/rain ahead
12:43:18.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft reverse sawtooth
12:47:01.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3900 ft

12:48:58.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:49:02.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:49:09.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile
12:50:52.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud run at 3500 ft
12:51:03.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:03.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:03.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:10.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:10.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:10.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:11.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:11.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:12.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:13.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:13.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:13.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:14.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:14.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:14.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:15.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:15.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:15.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:16.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:16.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:16.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:21.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:21.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:21.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:30.67	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:53:32.42	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:53:46.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
12:54:49.60	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:54:50.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:54:51.36	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:55:01.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:55:01.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:55:01.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:55:01.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:55:08.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:55:08.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:55:08.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:55:09.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:55:09.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:55:10.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:55:11.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:55:11.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:55:11.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:55:11.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:55:12.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:55:12.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:55:20.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:55:20.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:55:20.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:55:54.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:57:17.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent to 50 ft
13:00:08.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
13:02:11.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft
13:03:27.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 1500 ft
13:03:41.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud run
13:03:58.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:03:58.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:03:58.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:04.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:04.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:04.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:05.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:06.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:06.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:06.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:04:06.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:06.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:07.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:08.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:08.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:09.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:09.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:09.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:09.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:10.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:10.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:16.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:16.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:16.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:55.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 7
13:07:57.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:11:50.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:50.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:50.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:56.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:56.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:56.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:57.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:57.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:57.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:58.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:58.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:58.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:59.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:00.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:00.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:04.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:04.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:04.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:13:28.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:13:42.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb to FL 230
13:13:48.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:14:53.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 3000 ft
13:15:01.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:15:29.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** clopud top 4100 ft
13:15:43.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:44.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:44.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:44.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:49.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:49.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:49.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:50.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:50.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:51.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:52.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:52.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:52.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:53.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:53.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:53.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:54.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:54.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:54.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:55.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:55.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:15:56.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:00.40	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:16:02.14	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:16:03.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:03.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:03.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:17:28.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:20:39.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** still cirrus above

13:20:50.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** stratocumulus sheet below
13:21:12.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:22:22.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:27:04.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 6 will be from FL 230
13:27:37.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL 230 now
13:28:57.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
13:29:19.29	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:29:21.07	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:29:29.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:29.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:29.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:36.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:36.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:36.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:37.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:38.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:38.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:39.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:39.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:39.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:40.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:40.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:41.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:43.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:43.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:43.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:44.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:44.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:44.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:48.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:48.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:48.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:08.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:31:22.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:32:01.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 6
13:33:05.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:05.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:05.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:10.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:10.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:10.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:11.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:11.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:12.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:13.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:13.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:13.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:14.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:14.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:15.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:19.14	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:33:20.89	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:33:25.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:25.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:25.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:25.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:25.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:25.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:27.96	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:35:29.73	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:35:36.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:36.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:36.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:37.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:37.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:38.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:38.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:38.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:38.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:35:39.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:39.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:40.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:41.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:41.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:41.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:42.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:42.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:42.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:44.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:44.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:44.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:45.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:45.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:45.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:51.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:51.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:51.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:01.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 7
13:39:58.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:59.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:59.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:40:02.06	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:40:03.61	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:40:05.38	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:40:07.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:07.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:07.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:57.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:43:24.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:24.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:24.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:26.78	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:43:28.57	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:43:34.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:34.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:34.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:35.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:36.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:36.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:37.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:37.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:37.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:38.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:39.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:39.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:40.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:40.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:40.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:41.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:42.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:42.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:46.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:46.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:46.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:01.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 8
13:46:17.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde not released
13:47:04.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 8 now
13:47:09.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
13:47:55.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:47:55.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:47:55.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:47:57.40	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:47:59.19	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:48:02.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:02.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:02.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:50:20.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:51:42.69	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000

13:51:44.45	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:51:50.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:50.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:50.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:51.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:51.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:52.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:53.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:53.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:53.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:54.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:54.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:54.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:57.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:57.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:57.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:58.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:58.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:58.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:59.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:59.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:00.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:01.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:01.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:01.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:01.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:02.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:02.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:05.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:05.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:05.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:14.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:54:02.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 9
13:54:50.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:50.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:50.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:52.52	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:54:54.30	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:54:57.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:57.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:57.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:57:39.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:39.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:39.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:41.20	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:57:42.99	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:57:48.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:48.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:48.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:49.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:50.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:50.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:51.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:51.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:51.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:52.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:52.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:52.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:53.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:53.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:53.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:54.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:55.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:55.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:56.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:56.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:57.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:57.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:58.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

13:57:58.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:59.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:59.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:59.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:58:00.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:01.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:01.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:05.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:05.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:05.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:34.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:01:01.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** sonde 10
14:02:02.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:02.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:02.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:05.74	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:02:07.50	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:02:10.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:10.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:10.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:10.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:06:18.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:07:16.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:09:24.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run start of profile descent
14:09:37.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:37.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:37.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:39.91	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:09:41.71	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:09:48.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:48.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:48.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:48.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:49.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:49.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:50.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:50.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:50.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:51.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:51.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:52.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:52.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:52.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:52.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:53.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:53.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:54.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:56.65	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 20ms.
14:09:56.66	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 20ms.
14:09:58.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:58.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:58.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:59.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:59.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:00.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:00.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:00.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:00.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:01.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:01.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:02.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:02.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:02.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:02.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:02.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:03.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:04.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:04.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:04.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:10:04.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:04.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:05.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:05.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:05.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:06.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:06.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:09.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:09.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:09.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:15.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:15.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:15.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:20.12	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:10:21.88	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:11:52.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
14:14:48.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:15:08.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:08.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:08.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:09.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:10.83	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:15:12.62	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:15:15.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:15.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:15.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:07.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** patchy cirrus above
14:16:15.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** stratocumulus sheet below
14:16:59.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:59.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:59.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:17:01.39	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:17:03.14	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:17:04.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:17:04.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:17:04.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:17:33.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:22:21.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:22:30.17	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:22:31.98	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:22:42.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:42.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:42.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:47.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:47.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:47.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:48.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:48.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:49.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:49.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:49.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:49.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:49.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:50.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:50.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:51.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:51.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:51.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:52.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:52.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:53.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:54.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:54.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:54.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:55.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:55.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:56.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:23:00.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:00.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:23:00.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:15.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:23:15.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:23:15.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:23:20.09	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:23:21.86	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:23:28.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:28.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:28.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:51.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** 154 deg
14:23:59.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:26:16.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:26:16.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:26:16.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:26:17.92	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:26:19.65	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:26:21.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:21.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:21.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:39:01.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:01.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:01.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:06.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:06.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:06.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:07.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:07.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:08.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:08.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:08.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:08.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:09.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:09.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:10.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:10.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:10.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:10.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:11.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:11.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:12.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:17.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:39:17.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:39:17.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B415..**

Date 05/11/2008..

Operator's name JB.....

Page .1..... of

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
09:21								chiler off for transit
10:52		5000						chiller on
10:53			14	27	33	off	39	
11:01	r3	1800	15.2	38	77	39	44	
11:03	r3	1800	15.3	35	84	44	8	
11:12	r3	1800	15.3	36	45	17	40	
11:25			15	42	79	40	44	
11:26		800	15	41	86	44	8	
11:32								ver noisy trace, lots of drizzle about. stay lowRH for cloud run.
11:42								cvi set up run
11:43		3500	14.4	29	28	8		in cloud, neff min RH
12:13	p4	3400	14	31	33	10	43	straight to high RH for saw teeth
12:21								noisy above cloud as air clean, noisy below due to drizzle.
12:33								leave on above 5000ft, only going to 6500 sawtooth peaks
12:41								air in POC very clean
12:42					83	43	20	
12:44	p?				76	35	43	back to high rh (I thought a SLR was comin, profile instead)
12:53	r?	3300	14	32	84	43	20	drop to low for short in cloud run
13:04	r7	1300	14.7	35	49	20	43	go for cycle.

Wed 5 Nov 2008

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B415:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
MARSS	No MARSS log may have been created (Stuart Rogers was also running ARIES)
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS	2D-S / CAPS operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
CCN log	CCN operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	15 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_105754_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_115754_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_125754_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_135754_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_105748_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_115748_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_125748_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_135748_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_105746_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_115746_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_125746_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_135746_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_105751_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_115751_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_125751_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081105_r0_b415_135751_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.